

THE MODULE PERIODICITY OF SMARANDACHE CONCATENATED ODD SEQUENCE

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Abstract

In this paper we prove that the residue sequence of Smarandache concatenated odd sequence mod 3 is periodical.

Let p be a prime. For any integer a , let $\langle a \rangle_p$ denote the least nonnegative residue of a mod p . Further, for an integer sequence

$A = \{a(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, the sequence $\{\langle a(n) \rangle_p\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is called the residue sequence of A mod p , and denoted by $\langle A \rangle_p$.

In [1], Marimutha defined the Smarandache concatenated odd

sequence $S = \{s(n)\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$, where

$$(1) \quad s(1)=1, \quad s(2)=13, \quad s(3)=135, \quad s(4)=1357, \dots$$

In this paper we discuss the periodicity of $\langle S \rangle_p$. Clearly, if $p=2$ or 5 , then the residue sequence $\langle S \rangle_p$ is periodical.

We now prove the following result:

Theorem. If $p=3$, then $\langle S \rangle_p$ is periodical.

Prof. For any positive integer k , we have $10^k \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.

Hence, we see from (1) that

$$(2) \quad s(n) \equiv 1+3+5+\dots+(2n-1) = n^2 \pmod{3}.$$

Since

$$(3) \quad \langle n^2 \rangle_3 = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \text{ or } 2 \pmod{3}, \end{cases}$$

we find from (2) and (3) that

$$(4) \quad \langle s(n) \rangle_3 = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}; \\ 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \text{ or } 2 \pmod{3}, \end{cases}$$

Thus, by (4), the sequence $\langle S \rangle_3 = \{\langle s(n) \rangle_3\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ is periodical.

The theorem is proved.

Finally, we pose the following

Question. Is the residue sequence $\langle S \rangle_p$ periodical for every odd prime p ?

Reference:

I.H.Marimutha, "Smarandache concatenate type sequences", Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences, 16E (1997), No. 2, 225 - 226.